

PRACTICAL INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE-BASED LIFE METHODS FOR BONDED AIRFRAME STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to advance the state-of-the-art in both interlaminar fracture-based composite life methods, and related coupon-level test methods development. Specifically, a simplified fracture method was demonstrated on a new test problem and further development issues associated with long crack lengths and high growth rates were identified; the static ECT test was explored; ENF-based fatigue onset and growth tests were demonstrated; and it was recommended that 2D fabric materials be added to the scope statements of existing ASTM D30 interlaminar fracture standards, with appropriate caveats.

1 INTRODUCTION

Two of the main inhibitions to the use of interlaminar-fracture-based life methods for composite airframe structure are cost/span/complexity of the computational method and lack of established standard test methods for generation of initiation and growth design curves. The objectives of this U.S. Office of Naval Research (ONR)-funded effort are to advance the state-of-the-art in both areas.

2 SIMPLIFIED FRACTURE-BASED LIFE METHOD

While tremendous progress has been made over the past 30+ years in the field of interlaminar fracture mechanics (ILFM) based life methods for continuous-fiber laminated composites, efficient closed-form solutions are extremely limited, and numerical virtual-crack-closure (VCCT) methods remain computationally quite expensive. Thus, in this work a significant simplifying assumption regarding crack growth was made, to enable a far more efficient VCCT analysis to be used for practical life predictions of complex airframe structure under spectrum fatigue loading. The assumption is that the monotonically loaded strain energy release rate, G , along a pre-determined crack path, a , can be used to estimate the cyclic fatigue crack growth rate along that same path [1]. The major computational advantage of this assumption is that a single VCCT analysis can be used to construct a G vs a curve that is then used in a closed-form calculation with a traditional Palmgren-Miner's life method and Paris-Law relation from coupon testing to predict a complex spectrum fatigue life. As is common with laminated composite crack initiation/growth, the overall strain energy is separated into its opening, shear, and tearing modes (modes I, II, and III, respectively). For this project, much of the required input data for method validation already existed, while additional input data is being generated as part of the test methods development task. Regarding the observed gaps in the method implementation described in [1], this current project addresses issues related to input data, validation of the analysis methodology against a different element-level geometry for onset/growth/residual-strength, and complex crack path predictions. It does not address alternatives to either the BK mode interaction method [2] or Miner's Rule for spectrum damage accumulation.

3 TEST METHODS DEVELOPMENT

An equally vexing barrier to ILFM-based life methods is the lack of standardized coupon test methods, particularly for 2D fabric material that is the most common interface in bonded airframe

structure. For bonded semi-monocoque airframe structure, shear flow from skin to web is by far the most common type of loading for the bonded joint region. All three modes of fracture are present in this structural configuration. Since mode III is the least-mature mode of coupon testing it is one focus of this test methods development effort. A second focus area is mode II interlaminar fracture behavior in the presence of a fabric to film adhesive bondline. The full test matrix is shown in Table 1 along with relevant references [3,4]. The table illustrates where test standardization is particularly lacking (ECT FCGR will be addressed in a future paper). The combined test methods development expertise of LM and SwRI is particularly well-suited to addressing these challenges. The material tested in this project is a 350F-curing toughened epoxy with IM fiber in a crowfoot-satin weave, bonded with an epoxy film adhesive. The insert in all specimens was 0.0005-inch Teflon film. The non-standard mode III Edge-Crack Torsion (ECT) specimen and fixture configuration is shown in Figure 1. The following sub-sections detail experimental results, and recommendations regarding standardization.

Test Type	Test Method	Qty	Notes
Static ECT	Non-standard test per [4], plus new data reduction method	18	1/
Static ENF	ASTM D7905 (beyond tape-only scope)	54	2/
FCGR ENF	Similar to D6115, using D7905 fixture/specimen, R = 0.1	18	3/4/
FCGR ENF	Same as above, except R = -1	30	3/5/
FCGR ENF	Same as above, except Hi-Lo and Lo-Hi spectrum fatigue	12	3/6/

Notes: All D* test methods are per [3].

- 1 adhesive material lot, 6 replicates/condition, tested at CTA, RTA, and ETW conditions.
- 3 adhesive material lots, 6 replicates/lot, tested at CTA, RTA, and ETW conditions.
- Perform crack growth test similar to ASTM E647 in addition to standard crack initiation tests.
- 3 adhesive material lots, 6 replicates/lot, tested at RTA only.
- 3 adhesive material lots tested at RTA, 1 at CTA, and ETW; 6 replicates/lot.
- 1 adhesive material lot, 6 replicates per spectrum.

Table 1: Test matrix for input properties and test methods development.

Figure 1: Mode III ECT test specimen geometry and loading fixture.

3.1 Test Results and Observations

The non-standard ECT test method is based on several prior ASTM exploratory round-robins. The main unresolved problems with the ECT test at the conclusion of that circa mid/late 1990's work were (a) branching of the crack tip to ply interfaces other than the one at which the insert was located (all ASTM work focused on tape laminates without any adhesive bondline); (b) crack-length-dependence of GIIIc; and (c) the need for multiple coupons, tested at different crack lengths, in order to determine a compliance-based GIIIc result. This study attempts to address all three of these issues with (a) fabric

adherends; (b) a (relatively tough) bonded interface; and (c) an alternate data reduction scheme using laminate plate theory (LPT) assumptions rather than a pure multi-crack-length compliance calibration. Mode III critical strain energy release rate, G_{IIIc} , is determined using the compliance calibration (CC) and LPT data reduction methods as follows:

$$G_{IIIc}^{CC} = \frac{m(C_{sp} - C_{sys})P_{5\%}^2}{2Lb \left[1 - m \left(\frac{a}{b} \right) \right]} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{IIIc}^{LPT} = \frac{3(C_{sp} - C_{sys})^2 P_{5\%}^2}{Lb(C_{sub} - C_{sys})} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- Dimensions a , b , and L are as shown in Figure 1;
- C^* is the compliance (crosshead displacement over load over a given range, such as 10% and 50% of ultimate load) of the specimen (subscript “ sp ”), the load frame/fixture system (subscript “ sys ”, measured with a steel dummy specimen), or the sub-laminates (“ sub ”) after the failed specimens have been separated into two halves;
- m is the slope of multi-specimen plot of specimen stiffness $(C_{sp} - C_{sys})^{-1}$ vs a/b (following [4]); and
- $P_{5\%}$ is the lower of the 5% off-set or maximum failure load.

Note that while prior convention has been to use dimension l (the loaded portion of the width) rather than L in equations (1) and (2), a better physical understanding of the total energy and energy dissipation in the ECT specimen [7] suggests that this is incorrect, thus L (and in the LPT equation, b instead of W) is used. Also in this work, given that the LPT data reduction requires measurement of the fractured sub-laminate compliance, the in-plane shear stiffness for these sub-laminates is also determined via the relation:

$$G_{xy} = \frac{6Lb}{h^3(C_{sub} - C_{sys})} \quad (3)$$

Where h is the sub-laminate thickness, as shown in Figure 1. Despite the asymmetry of the overall specimen, the two symmetric but different sub-laminates in this study yield identical G_{xy} values, which are averaged from the two sub-laminates of each fracture specimen.

Static mode III fracture toughness results are summarized in Table 2, and representative fracture surfaces shown in Figure 2. Measured and theoretical G_{xy} values are shown in Table 3. A plot of G_{IIIc} vs non-dimensional crack length (a/b) is shown in Figure 3. As can be seen, this bond-assembled fabric coupon configuration still exhibits crack-length dependence, though not as severe as in tape. A logical hypothesis is that this dependence may be crack-tip shielding due to frictional effects. The variation in G_{IIIc} with a/b also confounds the CV’s for all specimens in each environment shown in Table 2. Separately determining CV for each crack length can be done by pooling across the three environments (yielding $N = 6$), resulting in the second set of CV’s shown in Table 2. These results suggest that since scatter is lowest at the intermediate $a/b = 0.3$ crack length perhaps that would be an ideal length on which to standardize. Regarding the fracture surfaces shown in Figure 2, there was variation in failure mode by environment, from adhesion at CTA, to cohesion at RTA, to a mix of adhesion and adherend failure at ETW. At ETW, when the crack did propagate into the adherend, two of the four specimens grew into the 0° ply while the others grew in the 45° ply. Assessing the two data reduction techniques (CC and LPT), it is seen in Table 2 and Figure 3 that the results differ by roughly 22%, with LPT always lower than the CC result. The LPT method is thus preferred from a conservatism, cost, and simplicity standpoint (but accuracy is an obvious issue, see [7]). Also, one interesting aspect of the LPT method is that testing the failed specimen halves to get their compliance allows in-plane laminate shear modulus to be generated, with those results shown in Table 3, illustrating fairly close agreement with the theoretical values from LPT, at least at RTA and ETW conditions. Finally, regarding crack-branching to other ply interfaces, simple stress analysis of the coupon configuration suggests that fiber strain in the most highly-loaded fabric ply is $\pm 3600 \mu\epsilon$, and shear strain on the outer 45° ply is roughly $7300 \mu\epsilon$ at $P = 1000$ lbf (RTA failure loads ranged from 976 – 1441 lbf) which, while below failure strains for this fabric material, are well into the range where intra-tow matrix cracking would be observed. Thus, crack-branching via matrix cracking cannot be ruled out.

Property	CTA	RTA	ETW	Property	CTA	RTA	ETW
G_{IIIc}^{CC} (psi-in)	16.71	21.05	13.18	G_{IIIc}^{LPT} (psi-in)	13.06	16.22	10.25
CV_{env} (%)	13.5	16.6	24.5	CV_{env} (%)	11.3	13.3	21.2
Nominal a/b :	0.2	0.3	0.4	Nominal a/b :	0.2	0.3	0.4
$CV_{a/b}$ (%)	16.1	4.4	9.5	$CV_{a/b}$ (%)	13.3	4.6	8.6

Notes:

- N = 6 for each mean value. Nominal $a = 0.35, 0.50,$ and 0.75 inch at each condition (N = 2 each).
- N = 6 for the $CV_{a/b}$ separated out by crack length (by pooling CTA, RTA, and ETW specimens).

Table 2: Static mode III ECT test results summary.

Figure 2: Representative mode III ECT fracture surfaces.

Property	CTA	RTA	ETW
G_{xy} -meas (Msi)	4.84	4.26	4.05
CV (%)	2.8	7.5	7.0
G_{xy} -pred (Msi)	4.16	4.15	4.10
meas/pred	1.16	1.03	0.99

Table 3: Static G_{xy} test results summary and comparison to LPT predictions.

Figure 3: G_{IIIc} still exhibits crack-length dependence despite use of 0/45 fabric and adhesive.

Static mode II fracture toughness results are summarized in Table 4, and all the various types of fracture surfaces shown in Figure 4 through Figure 6. In Table 4, both non-pre-cracked (from the insert) and pre-cracked results are shown. As with most solid laminate tape (and as opposed to bond-assembled fabric) ENF testing to date, the result from the pre-crack (PC) is of lower magnitude and has generally been deemed more physically

representative of mode II fracture behavior at a laminate-level, due to the formation of microcracks ahead of the macro-level crack tip, and distance from the (relatively blunt) insert material. However, as seen in Table 4 for this study, the PC CV's are extraordinarily high, while the non-pre-cracked (NPC) CV's are somewhat more reasonable. The other important aspect of this testing was the careful observation and discrimination of failure modes that SwRI was able to accomplish. Figure 4 through Figure 6 illustrate that there was variation in failure mode both by environment and by adhesive lot. In

addition, low-magnification optical microscopy seemed to indicate that fabric adherend failures involved breaking fibers at the tops of the weave undulations, with the crack front propagating along the fibers within the tow for some fraction of the unit cell followed by fiber breakage and a jump to the next tow. In this manner, cracks tended to propagate just below, rather than at, the ply- or adhesive-interfaces.

In order better to understand the source of the large G_{IIc}^{PC} variation, bar charts by lot and environment were created as shown in Figure 7. As can be seen, all three adhesive lots, and all environments exhibited significant variability, with an almost bi-modal distribution in the case of Lot A. Except for the case of ETW, Lot C, where the failures were all 100% adherend right from the start (these are also lower in Figure 7 compared to Lots A and B), fracture surface/failure mode differences did not track well with the high vs low values. However, given that the static G_{IIc} for the fabric adherend itself (measured in prior work and cited in figure) is in the middle of this large range of values, it is still likely that a mix of adherend and bondline failures is to blame.

Property	CTA	RTA	ETW	Property	CTA	RTA	ETW
G_{IIc}^{PC} (psi-in)	12.39	19.11	13.92	G_{IIc}^{NPC} (psi-in)	18.61	24.83	15.89
CV_{env} (%)	36.9	15.7	40.2	CV_{env} (%)	15.7	10.9	18.3

Notes:

- N = 18 for each mean value. N = 6 for each of 3 adhesive lots. Only one prepreg mat'l lot used.

Table 4: Static mode II ENF test results summary.

Figure 4: Static mode II RTA ENF fracture surfaces.

Figure 5: Static mode II CTA ENF fracture surfaces.

Figure 6: Static mode II ETW ENF fracture surfaces.

Figure 7: Adhesive-lot and environmental variations in G_{IIc}^{PC} .

Mode II constant-amplitude fatigue delamination onset testing was essentially performed on every fatigue crack growth specimen at both $R = 0.1$ and $R = -1$. Details of the test fixture, data acquisition system, clip gage, pre-cracking, crack growth compliance measurement algorithm, ASTM E647-inspired load-controlled G-increasing methodology, non-ambient temperature chamber and control, etc., and are all available upon request, subject to certain data restrictions. Due to the small measured changes in compliance with crack growth, the standard D7905 support span of 4-inches was increased to 5-inches, to yield more compliance. In mode II, development of a fatigue-onset G vs N curve was found to be particularly problematic, due to the fact that growth either occurred or didn't in a very small range of applied fatigue loading. Thus, it was difficult to intentionally generate onset data at a targeted number of fatigue cycles. Nonetheless, given the number of fatigue coupons tested in this study, such curves were generated, albeit with significant scatter. $R = 0.1$ curves at all three environmental conditions are shown in Figure 8, with RTA seen to be the most conservative. The $R = -1$ curve is shown in Figure 9. RTA curves at both $R = 0.1$ and $R = -1$ are shown comparatively in Figure 10, with $R = -1$ more conservative. Failure modes at onset were predominantly adherend at CTA and RTA (except for Lot A $R = -1$, where all six coupons exhibited cohesive growth), and cohesion at ETW.

Mode II constant-amplitude fatigue crack growth testing was accomplished by running in G-increasing mode as the crack grew from approximately 1.2 to 2.0 inches, then shifting the specimen over in the fixture to continue the test. A typical a vs N curve is shown in Figure 11, and typical da/dN vs ΔG for one G-increasing segment is shown in Figure 12. An interesting aspect of mode II fatigue testing is the definition of ΔG and/or N (e.g., does a complete, fully-reversed load cycle yield $\Delta G_{II} = G_{II}^{max} - G_{II}^{min} = 2 * G_{II}^{max}$, does $N = N$ or $2 * N$, or is some other convention used). For plotting da/dN data this study used the metallic mode I convention of plotting $R = 0.1$ data vs ΔG and $R = -1$ data vs G_{max} (assumes that the negative-shear loads did not contribute to crack growth). In viewing the subsequent plots, it is easy enough to consider how they would look if the alternate plotting convention were used, e.g., $\Delta G = 2 * G_{II}^{max}$, though be aware that the curves don't simply translate since they are plotted in log-log space. Figure 13 shows $R = 0.1$ and $R = -1$ data plotted in this manner for the 12 RTA Lot C specimens (about 9 or so of the specimens had multiple segments tested). Figure 14 shows the multi-lot result for RTA, $R = 0.1$, including the power-law curve fit. Figure 15 shows the multi-lot result for RTA, $R = -1$, this time plotted against $\Delta G = 2 * G_{II}^{max}$, including the power-law curve fit. As can be seen in Figure 14 and Figure 15, scatter is an issue with this test. Finally, Figure 16 illustrates the differences in mode II fatigue crack growth rate behavior at different environments (CTA, RTA, and ETW), with ETW appearing to be the most critical.

Mode II hi-lo and lo-hi spectrum fatigue crack growth testing was conducted to interrogate the

possible crack growth-retardation effects that would confound the use of a simple Miner's Rule type of life prediction methodology. As suspected, significant retardation effects were noted in RTA R = 0.1 mode II testing, as seen in Figure 17.

Figure 8: Mode II ENF fatigue onset results at R = 0.1 and all environments.

Figure 9: Mode II ENF fatigue onset results at R = -1, RTA environment.

Figure 10: Mode II ENF fatigue onset comparison of R = 0.1 and -1 curves.

Figure 11: Typical a vs N response (red curve-fit used to determine da/dN).

Figure 12: Typical da/dN vs ΔG for a single crack-length segment.

Figure 13: da/dN vs ΔG or G_{II}^{max} curves for RTA Lot C.

Figure 14: da/dN vs ΔG for $R = 0.1$, RTA, all adhesive lots.

Figure 15: da/dN vs ΔG (not G_{II}^{max}) for $R = -1$, RTA, all adhesive lots.

Figure 16: da/dN vs ΔG for $R = 0.1$, all three environments.

Figure 17: Lo-Hi and Hi-Lo spectrum fatigue crack growth effects, a vs N .

3.2 Recommendations Regarding Standardization of Coupon Test Methods

As noted in the prior sub-section observations, several challenges remain in terms of standardizing the tests performed in this project. Thus, the following recommendations for ASTM standards revisions and development, as well as pre-standardization research are made:

- Extend the scopes of D5528, D6115, and D7905 to include 2-dimensional woven fabrics as well as unidirectional tape. These revisions should, of course, include appropriate caveats regarding crack branching and self-similar crack growth along the somewhat more tortuous path between woven layers. Do not extend these scopes to adhesively bonded specimens since this violates LEFM, and this study has shown undesirable failure mode variability, at least in mode II testing.
- Consider standardization of the static ECT configuration using a single $a/b = 0.3$ crack length and LPT data reduction technique, at least for fabric materials, and subject to further exploratory round-robin testing without an adhesive interface.
- Consider standardization of an ENF-based mode II fatigue delamination onset test method, modified for increased compliance, for a set range of R-ratios, once cycle counting in the presence of load-reversals is clarified/defined.
- Continue development of mode II FCGR test methods, with further research into appropriate G-

control methods, further exploratory round-robins not confounded by an adhesive layer, different tape and fabric forms, environments, etc. All this to get suitably low-variability and repeatable results.

4 ANALYSIS METHOD VERIFICATION

A bonded lap joint, representing a generic skin-to-flange detail, is planned to be tested in far-field shear loading in a manner similar to, but more simplified than prior FAA-funded work [6]. The intended test configuration, shown in Figure 18, features a flat adherend (skin or web termination) bonded to a tapered adherend (flange). This element-level test was modeled in ABAQUS™ and fatigue life predicted using the simplified ILM-based life method described in section 2 and [1]. Figure 19 and Figure 20 illustrate the preliminary static ILM analysis results from ABAQUS™. The preliminary model showed a linear load-displacement response up to the growth of a crack in the bondline. The ILM solution predicted a mixed mode shear loading (Mode I and Mode II) at the free edge of the bonded area where the crack initiates. Crack initiation occurred at approximately 13,500 pounds of applied load in the free edge of the flat adherend near the upper end of the bondline. Additional load then caused some incremental crack growth first along the length of the bondline, then began to propagate into the bondline at approximately 15,000 lb applied load. At this point, the analysis failed to meet the convergence criteria necessary for a statically determinate model. Future model developments will enable a longer crack growth solution, which will be necessary for the simplified ILM-based life analysis method being completed. The rate at which strain energy builds up at the crack tip is extracted from the static analysis model results for all three modes of crack growth. Figure 21 shows the results of this output for the crack lengths achieved by the analysis for Mode 1 crack growth. As load is initially applied to the specimen, strain energy will build up following the solid blue curve which represents no damage accumulation (damage area of 0 in²). Then, at initiation (13,500 lb), the next cracked area appears (0.031 in²). It was assumed that the load distribution achieved in the initial state would maintain the same shape, but it would pass through the strain energy at the crack growth load for that given area (orange dashed curve ending at 15,000 lb). As the analysis achieves longer crack lengths, more data will be extracted to fill out a full load vs. strain energy plot to be used by the simplified ILM-based life analysis method.

Figure 18: Bonded shear joint planned test configuration.

Figure 19: Preliminary static model results.

Figure 20: Preliminary ILFM results from static model.

Figure 21: Static analysis load vs. strain energy data extraction for Mode I.

Static delamination toughness, delamination onset life, fatigue crack growth life, and static residual strength after two lifetimes of generic wing root bending spectrum fatigue will eventually be predicted for the normalized spectrum is shown in Table 5. The ILFM-based fatigue life solution shown in this paper was performed on the limited initial model results that were achieved so far. Given that the initial analysis had only been completed for positive shear loading only (positive enforced displacement boundary condition), the target spectrum was clipped such that only positive or zero minimum forces were analyzed. Figure 22 shows the results for cycles to delamination onset as a function of several reference loads for the modified spectrum. The initial results show that a reference load of 9,000 pounds or less does not achieve crack growth. The current implementation of the ILFM-based fatigue life solution also applies a single cycle to the reference load if all cycles are completed to perform a “go/no go” check of the residual strength of the joint. This step revealed that the joint has enough residual strength for the lower reference loads. Reference loads above 9,000 pounds satisfied the delamination onset criteria during fatigue cycles. A strong dependence on reference load was shown as it was increased up through 11,500 pounds.

The fatigue crack growth life portion of the analysis was rather limited due to the small amount of data generated by the static analysis model. A mixed mode crack growth solution was seen for analyses where the reference load was greater than 9,000 lb. Figure 23 shows the number of cycles required to advance the crack from initiation to the extent of the static solution and the average crack growth rate. Given the limited data from the initial static solution, the crack growth portion of the analysis completed in a very few number of cycles. The crack growth cycles to the end of the analysis was highly sensitive to the reference load. This was largely due to the high crack growth rate calculated by the mixed mode solution.

Based on the initial results of the bonded shear lap joint analysis:

- Significant effort and expertise required for static solution results that capture long crack lengths;

- Positive shear loading currently captured, need to capture negative shear loading;
- Cyclic analysis utilized a B-K method of determining mixed mode effects, as in the static solution;
- Cycles to onset based on Miner’s Rule for damage accumulation;
- Cycles to onset is sensitive to the reference load of the spectrum;
- Mixed mode crack growth solution showed a high average crack growth rate; and
- High crack growth rate and small amount of crack area from static solution lead to small number of cycles to the end of the initial solution.

Test results for the element test configuration shown in Figure 18 and experimental validation results will be reported in a future publication.

Sequence	Min Force/Pref	Max Force/Pref	Cycles
1	-0.31	+1.00	1
2	-0.06	+0.65	135
3	-0.2	+0.85	14
4	-0.25	+0.95	3
5	-0.16	+0.75	44
6	-0.22	+0.90	3
7	+0.04	+0.55	300

One block shown. Equal to 80 flight hours

One life = 100 blocks = 50,000 cycles

Two lives = 200 blocks = 100,000 cycles

Table 5: Generic wing root bending spectrum, normalized to Pref = 1.0.

Figure 22: Fatigue delamination onset model results.

Figure 23: Preliminary ILFM-based crack growth solution.

5 SUMMARY

This paper has advanced the state-of-the-art in both interlaminar fracture-based composite life methods, and related coupon-level test methods development. Specifically,

- The simplified fracture method was demonstrated on a new test problem and further development issues associated with long crack lengths and high growth rates were identified;
- The static ECT test was explored, a standardization path suggested, as well as further research;
- The shortcomings of the ENF-based fatigue onset and growth test were demonstrated and further changes to address these suggested; and
- It was recommended that 2D fabric materials be added to the scope statements of existing ASTM D30 interlaminar fracture standards, with appropriate caveats.

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